

Investigation of an atmospheric pressure radio frequency helium planar plasma source in humid ambient air

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Abstract

Atmospheric pressure radio frequency (RF) helium plasma jets operating in open air are capable of producing abundant reactive species and are widely used in biomedical applications. A planar atmospheric pressure RF plasma is studied by diagnostics and numerical modelling in this work. A novel methodology with reduced computational time and complexity is developed by converting a two-dimensional (2D) plasma fluid model into a series of one dimensional (1D) models. The numerical model reproduced the electrical characteristics and the emission spectroscopy dynamics of the discharge in good agreement with experimental measurements. Furthermore, the air influence on the kinetics of short-lived species and long-lived species is investigated numerically. It is shown that electrons are the most abundant negative species in the discharge and their density decreases with air impurities. The increasing air impurities along the discharge channel can weaken the electric field resulting in lower ionization near the outlet, and even possibly destabilizing the discharge. Reactive oxygen species are mainly present as atomic oxygen. H_2O_2 is produced in the gas phase through the recombination of OH radicals and destructed by collisions with He_m . It is revealed that the important for biomedical applications singlet oxygen $\text{O}_2(a)$ is primarily generated by direct excitation of O_2 and destructed through recombination with $\text{O}(^1\text{S})$. The presented model can be used to study the kinetics of reactive species in atmospheric pressure RF plasma jets working in humid ambient air typical of biomedical applications.

Keywords: atmospheric pressure plasma, humid air impurities, gas flow dynamics, plasma fluid modelling

1. Introduction

Atmospheric pressure RF plasmas have significant potential in a wide range of applications such as sterilization, surface modification, and biomedicine [1–3]. In practice, many plasma sources are operated in the open air, due to reduced operational costs. This results in rather complex chemistry due to the plasma working in the presence of air impurities that can lead to the formation of undesirable products and discharge instabilities [4–7]. To meet the requirements of different applications, air impurity influences on plasma physics and chemical kinetics need to be investigated in order to understand and optimize the plasma behaviour [8,9]. In order to conduct these investigations, plasma modelling can complement experimental plasma diagnostics [10]. In this way, insights on plasma physics, chemical reactions initiated by the discharge and important reactive species formed in the effluent can be obtained. In this work the plasma fluid model (PFM) which is widely employed to study the discharge physics and chemistry in atmospheric pressure plasmas is used [8,11,12].

Although there have been several experimental studies on atmospheric pressure RF helium plasmas working in open air [13–15] aimed at the investigation of the dynamics of produced species, it is very challenging to obtain the concentrations of produced species with good spatial and temporal resolution. Plasma modelling overcomes those limitations. Schroter et al. [16] studied the chemical kinetics in an atmospheric pressure RF plasma with a zero-dimensional (0D) fluid model of He/humid air chemistry and ultra-violet absorption spectroscopy. Sun et al. [17] developed a 0D fluid model of He/humid air chemistry to study the production of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONs) at different air impurities. Liu et al. investigated humid air influences on RF helium plasmas confined in a closed chamber by a 1D plasma fluid model, without considering the influences of back diffusion of ambient air [18].

In this work, the discharge region of an atmospheric pressure RF helium plasma containing humid air impurities is investigated. The applied voltage parameters for the plasma operating in α -mode are determined. The α -mode is desirable for biomedical and other applications due to its uniformity, high temporal and spatial stability, and low gas heating. Electrical and emission spectroscopy measurements of the discharge are compared to numerical results. Once good agreement is obtained the model is used to provide insight into phenomena and quantities that are too difficult or impossible to measure experimentally. Specifically, the sustaining mechanisms of the discharge, and the density of plasma species as a function of air impurity content are investigated. The study and methods presented contribute to the understanding of atmospheric pressure RF helium plasma jets in humid ambient air conditions and their operation in α -mode.

This manuscript is arranged as follows. The experimental setup is given in section 2. The numerical model description is given in section 3. The numerical model consists of three major parts. The first part is an equivalent electrical circuit model used to estimate the parasitic capacitance coupled to the PFM. The second part is a 2D gas dynamic model (GDM) used to calculate air impurity content

along the discharge. The results from the GDM and the parasitic capacitance are fed to the third major part of the model, the PFM. In this work a novel method of converting a 2D PFM model into a series of 1D PFM models has been developed. The method is based on determining the sections (or domains) of the device for which the level of air impurities is almost constant. This is possible inside the gap where the discharge is uniform in one dimension. Each separate domain can be treated as a 1D problem. This saves computational time and complexity. Section 4 starts with experimental results that provide input parameters and comparison to the results of the numerical model. Then it moves into numerical work with the results of the GDM for the level of air impurities and the number of domains across the device. Furthermore, the numerical results from the PFM of the effect of the concentration of air impurities on plasma species and the discharge dynamics are presented. The conclusions and summary are given in section 5.

2. Experimental setup

Figure 1 describes the plasma source and diagnostic setup based on optical emission spectroscopy. The planar RF plasma source consisted of a 10 mm \times 30 mm planar powered electrode and grounded electrode, with a 0.5 mm thick dielectric layer attached to the powered electrode. The gap (or the discharge region) between the grounded electrode and dielectric is 2 mm. The dielectric layer is made of alumina with a dielectric constant of 10. An RF (13.56 MHz) generator (ADTEC AX-600III-A-NV1) was used to ignite and sustain the plasma with an L type automatic impedance matching unit (ADTEC AMV-1000-EN). Voltage and current were detected with a Vigilant Sensor RF voltage-current probe and recorded by a Lecroy oscilloscope with a bandwidth of 650 MHz. Helium gas flow was controlled by a Bronkhorst EL-FLOW mass flow controller and fixed at 2 SLM.

The emission spectra were recorded with a spectrometer (HORIBA FHR 1000) and Andor iDus 420-OE CCD camera. The HORIBA spectrometer used the 2400 grooves/mm grating and the Andor CCD camera conducted 50 accumulations for each time-integrated spectrum acquisition. The resolution of the spectrometer was measured by a low-pressure mercury lamp (Pen-Ray) at wavelength of 435.83 nm to be 0.014 nm.

Time resolved spectroscopy was adopted to investigate the discharge dynamics by means of a Hamamatsu C8484 ICCD camera with a digital delay generator (DG535, Stanford Research), synchronized with the discharge. The spatial resolution of the system with the use of ICCD camera and zoom objective at $\times 10$ amplification factor was estimated to be 30 μm . The ICCD gate time and accumulation number were set at 5 ns and 5000 respectively. The delay generator was used to set 16 consecutive trigger timings from $T + 0$ ns to $T + 75$ ns with an interval of 5 ns, as shown in Figure A1.

Photon counting techniques were used to detect the time resolved excited states emission behavior with 5 ns resolution. These excited states include OH radicals (309 nm), N_2 excited states (337 nm), N_2^+ excited states (391 nm), He I (707 nm), O I (777 nm). Optical signals from different excited states emission were filtered out by using a monochromator (Zolix Omni- $\lambda 750$). The current signal of

the detector afterward was sent to a photon counting multichannel analyzer SR430 (Stanford Research), triggered by the same delay generator (DG535). The overall jitter of delay generator was less than 1 ns.

Figure 1: Schematic of experiment setup including plasma source and diagnostic apparatus.

3. Modelling setup

The model is developed to study the discharge dynamics inside the gap where there is limited air mixing. The discharge is considered homogeneous along the z axis and this is confirmed experimentally. The flowchart of the numerical procedure and comparison to the experimental results is shown in Figure 2. The modelling starts with the determination of the parasitic capacitance of the source and air impurities. The parasitic capacitance originates from the cable, plasma source enclosure, etc. This capacitance can be obtained by electrical characteristic measurements matched to an equivalent electrical circuit model. The air impurities are computed with a 2D GDM. The parasitic capacitance and the results of the GDM are inputs to the plasma fluid model (PFM) for the discharge. The model runs in COMSOL Multiphysics® simulation package [19]. The electrical characteristics (voltage, current, and phase shift) and emission dynamics are compared and matched to experimental results.

Figure 2: Work flow and matching of PFM results to experimental results. V, I, ϕ are voltage, current, and the phase shift between them.

3.1 Equivalent circuit model

Due to the nonlinear behaviour of the RF plasma sheath, the current passing in the gap can contain harmonics of the fundamental applied RF frequency [20,21]. Fourier transform harmonics analysis of the current waveform shows a dominating 97.6% fundamental harmonic, which is typical for α -mode discharges in atmospheric pressure [22]. This means that the current exhibits an almost sinusoidal waveform and the plasma can be presented by an equivalent circuit model developed in [22]. In order to take into account the real electrical properties of the source, a parasitic capacitor (C_{para}) [23,24] in parallel to the plasma device, has to be added in the equivalent circuit as shown in Figure 3. Similar external circuit models for atmospheric pressure RF helium plasmas have also been shown in the literature [24,25]. C_{para} includes capacitance from coaxial cables, metal enclosure, etc. It can be obtained from the subtraction of the total capacitance of the dielectric layer C_d and gap layer C_g from the total capacitance of the device without plasma by the calculation of the slope of V-I characteristics. In practice, C_{para} is calculated from Equation (1):

$$C_{para} = \frac{I}{\omega V} - \frac{C_d C_g}{C_d + C_g} \quad (1)$$

where ω is the angular frequency of the applied voltage V and I is the current when there is no discharge.

Figure 3: Equivalent circuit model for atmospheric pressure RF plasma source system.

3.2 Gas dynamic and plasma fluid model

As the plasma is operated at atmospheric pressure, air invades into the source through back diffusion. At the entrance the plasma gas starts as almost pure helium but acquires more impurities close to the exit of the gap (at 10 mm). This allows for segmenting the simulation space into a number of domains based on the level of air in each region (see Figure 4a). Each distinct domain is defined as the region where the level of air impurities (expressed in ppm) along the x axis can be treated as a constant. Since the experimental results show the discharge along z axis is homogeneous, each domain can be solved as a 1D plasma problem (along the y axis). This approach is computationally efficient compared to solving the 2D problem. The total level of air impurities at each domain is the air back diffusion (denoted as Air_i in Figure 4) calculated through a two-dimensional steady state GDM plus the constant air traces from the helium bottle (as given by the supplier and denoted as Air_{bottle} in Figure 4). For each domain defined in Figure 4a, 1D PFM is solved (see Figure 4b). As it will be explained in the next subsection accumulation effects are taken into consideration by using the densities of a domain as the input conditions for the next one.

Figure 4: Flow chart from the GDM to the PFM: (a) 2D gas dynamic model is used to obtain air impurity distribution; (b) 1D plasma fluid model implements plasma simulation with air impurities.

3.2.1 Gas dynamic model (GDM)

The GDM calculates the air impurities due to back diffusion across the plasma device. This is done by solving a steady-state multi-component mass transport equation, without considering the chemical reaction term. The aforementioned equations are coupled with the conservation of total mass and momentum that give the mass average velocity of the mixture. These equations and their boundary conditions are described in detail in a previous study [26]. In Figure 5, the geometry used for the GDM is presented. The device is depicted with a red color. The Helium flows into the device from the left inlet (boundary IA) at a flow rate of 2 SLM. Around the device (see boundaries: CD-DE-EF-FG), the mole fraction of air is considered to be one. Furthermore, at these boundaries the pressure is set to 1

atmosphere. The plasma device boundaries GH-HI and AB-BC are considered as solid surfaces and the no-slip condition is imposed.

Figure 5: Simulation domain for the gas dynamic model. The plasma device is drawn with a red color, while the surrounding air with black lines.

3.2.2 Plasma fluid model (PFM)

For the plasma description, a series of 1D PFM (along y axis) are used. The simulation domain for this model is shown in Figure A2. The electron density and electron energy are described from the continuity equation in the drift-diffusion approximation, while the heavy species (neutral, excited, and ion species) from the multi-component diffusion equations. The aforementioned equations are coupled with the Poisson equation for the description of the electric field. The equations and their boundary conditions are described in detail in a previous study [27] with the addition of the C_{para} connected to the plasma source (see Figure 3). The plasma chemistry and species considered in this study are the same as in [27]. Specifically, more than 500 reaction channels are considered with a total of 59 species (helium, nitrogen, oxygen, and water, see Table 1). The secondary electron emission coefficient from the solid surfaces (dielectric and metal) is considered to be 0.01, as with this value the simulation results give the best agreement with the experimental results.

Table 1: Species considered in the PFM.

Category	Species
Electrons	e
Helium	He^+ , He_2^+ , He, He_m , $He(3s^3S)$, $He(2p^3P)$, He_2^*
Nitrogen	$N_2(B)^+$, N_2^+ , N_4^+ , N, N_2 , $N_2(v)$, $N_2(A)$, $N_2(B)$, $N_2(a)$, $N_2(C)$

Oxygen	$O_2^+, O_4^+, O^-, O_2^-, O_3^-, O, O_2, O_3, O(^1S), O(^1D), O_2(v), O_2(a), O_2(b)$
Water	$H_2O^+, H_2O_3^+, H_3O^+, H_4O_2^+, H_5O_2^+, H_7O_3^+, H_9O_4^+, H_{11}O_5^+,$ $H_{13}O_6^+, H_{15}O_7^+, H_{17}O_8^+, H_{19}O_9^+, H_3O_2^-, H_5O_3^-, H_2O$
Others	$H^+, H_2^+, OH^+, HeH^+, H^-, OH^-, H_2O_2^-, H, H_2, OH, OH(A), HO_2, H_2O_2$

He_m represents $He(2^3S)$ and $He(2^1S)$; He_2^* represents $He_2(a^3\Sigma_u^+)$; $N_2(v)$ represents the vibrational excited states of $N_2(v=1-10)$; $N_2(A)$ represents $N_2(A^3\Sigma_u^+)$; $N_2(B)$ represents $N_2(B^3\Pi_g)$, $N_2(W^3\Delta_u)$ and $N_2(B^3\Sigma_u^-)$; $N_2(a)$ represents $N_2(a^1\Sigma_u^-)$, $N_2(a^1\Pi_g)$ and $N_2(W^1\Delta_u)$; $N_2(C)$ represents $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$, $N_2(E^3\Sigma_g^+)$ and $N_2(a^1\Sigma_u^+)$; $O_2(a)$ represents $O_2(a^1\Delta_g)$; $O_2(b)$ represents $O_2(b^1\Sigma_g^+)$; $O_2(v)$ represents $O_2(v=1-4)$.

The densities of the background gases (He, N_2 , O_2 , H_2O) are calculated from the GDM (see Figure 9 and Table A1) for all domains. For the rest of the species and for the first domain (D1) the the initial densities are set to 10^{13} m^{-3} . It should be mentioned that for low impurities (such as D1) the initial densities do not affect the final results [27]. In order to account for accumulation effects the final species densities from solving the PFM of a domain become the initial conditions for the next domain. The initial densities in subsequent domains (D2-D6) are taken from the result of the 1D PFM simulations of the previous domain. It is also worth noting that due to very low gas speed ($\sim 0.84 \text{ m/s}$) compared to the ionization wave speed, the transport of species due to the gas flow and diffusion can be neglected as their effects are minimal.

For the PFM a mesh size of $0.12 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ is located in the region of the plasma and a larger mesh size of $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ is set in the region of the dielectrics. A mesh independency analysis was performed to ensure that a denser mesh does not increase significantly the accuracy of the results. The model equations were solved using the plasma module (for the PFM) and the chemical reaction engineering module (for the GDM) of the COMSOL Multiphysics® simulation package on a server with 16 core processors (Intel Xenon E5-2667 V4 3.2 GHz), 252 GB ram and 5.5 TB hard drive. The equations for the GDM and the PFM are discretized by the Galerkin finite element method using linear element shape functions, and the resulting system is solved using the direct solver PARDISO. For the time integration (PFM) the backward Euler method is used. A total time period of $100 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$ was calculated during the plasma modelling and it required about 6-8 days to be completed.

4. Results and discussion

The section starts with experimental results that provide input parameters needed for the development of the numerical model. The gas flow rate is set at 2 slm for experiments and simulations.

4.1 Experimental results

The plasma source is studied in terms of electrical characteristics, emission dynamics, and gas temperature. These studies provide input parameters such as C_{para} and the gas temperature (see Appendix B) for developing a realistic numerical model.

4.1.1 Electrical characteristics

The electrical characteristics including voltage and current are presented in Figure 6. The discharge is initially ignited as RF α -mode at an RMS voltage of 218 V and RMS current 0.44 A, corresponding to RF input power 10 W. The input power deposited in the plasma can be calculated by Equation 2:

$$P = V_{rms} I_{rms} \cos(\Phi_{V-I}) \quad (2)$$

where V_{rms} , I_{rms} , Φ_{V-I} are the RMS value of voltage, current, and phase shift between current and voltage respectively.

When the input power is increased from 10 W to 30 W, the RMS voltage rises from 218 to 331 V, RMS current from 0.48 to 0.70 A, deposited power from 2.2 to 14 W, and phase shift from -88.76° to -86.7° . The small difference in the phase shift is caused due to the resistive impedance of the discharge. When the input power exceeds 35 W, the discharge is transformed into γ -mode. The γ -mode of plasma produces excessive heat with high current and damages the electrodes. Thus γ -mode should be avoided for the operation of this plasma source. Similar phenomena were observed in [28,29] for atmospheric pressure RF plasma sources. For bio-applications, α -mode is the appropriate working mode because it achieves uniform treatment with relatively low gas temperatures. Once the parameters for the operation in the α -mode were established the subsequent experiments and simulations presented in this manuscript were conducted at an input power of 30 W, a gas flow rate of 2 SLM and a gas temperature of 375 K.

Based on the equivalent circuit model and the I/V slope with plasma off presented in Figure 6, a C_{para} of 22.65 pF was obtained for this plasma source and used in the PFM.

Figure 6: Electrical characteristics of the atmospheric pressure RF plasma source. The points corresponding to voltage at 331 V in the dashed square were used to compare with simulations.

4.1.2 Emission dynamics

As shown in Figure 7, time resolved spectroscopy was performed with an ICCD camera to investigate the time dependent emission patterns of the discharge.

Figure 7: Time resolved emission pattern of atmospheric pressure RF planar discharge with a helium flow rate of 2 SLM and an input power of 30 W. The corresponding RF voltage signals of trigger timings are shown in

Figure A1.

The overall emission evolves in a periodic fashion following the RF applied voltage with the formation of bright layers near the bottom and top electrodes. Two peaks are found for both emission layers around $T+10$ ns and $T+45$ ns, occurring in the times of sheath expansion/collapse where electrons

are driven towards the plasma bulk/electrodes respectively [30]. There is approximately a 0.4 mm gap between the electrode and brightest emission layer, which is the region of sheath (adjacent to the electrode boundary) and its extension to the plasma bulk. Since very few electrons exist in the sheath, there are very few collisions for excitation which results in low emission intensity. The bottom emission layer shows a higher intensity than the top one. This might be because of the slight asymmetry of the plasma source i.e. larger grounded electrode area than the powered electrode area due to imperfections during manufacturing and/or the SEEC of different boundaries. Similar phenomena were observed in the literature [13].

Figure 8: Optical emission diagnostics of the atmospheric pressure RF helium plasma: (a) emission spectra in the range of 200-900 nm. The spectrum was measured for the emission which is spatially average along the discharge gap and integrated for 50 accumulations with exposure time of 0.5 s.

The emission spectrum was acquired in the range of 200-900 nm (see Figure 8). Atomic lines including He I, O I, H β , H α lines and molecular bands containing OH(A-X), N $_2$ (C-B), N $_2^+$ (B-X) bands are observed in the spectrum. The impurities from the gas bottle and back diffusion of ambient air into discharge zone give rise to all those lines and bands (with the exception of the He I lines).

4.2 GDM results

The 2D gas dynamics were studied to find out the content of ambient air diffusion into the device. After reaching a steady state, the velocity distribution and air mole fraction are obtained, shown in Figure 9(a) and Figure 9(b), respectively. The penetration length of helium gas agrees with the experimental observation of plasma effluent length. Due to the buoyancy force, the helium flow plunges into air while going forwards and upwards.

Figure 9: Gas flow dynamics: (a) velocity distribution and (b) air mole fraction in the helium-air mixture.

The device has been segmented into 6 domains based on the air impurity level due to back diffusion as shown in Table 2. The total air impurities that include gas bottle impurities are summarized in Table A1. As expected, the gas is almost pure helium for the majority of the length (8 mm) of the device. A drastic increase in air impurity level is found close to the outlet of the device. These six domains correspond to the six 1D PFM simulations.

Table 2: Level of air across the discharge gap appearing due to air back diffusion

Domain	x (mm)	Level of air (ppm)
D1	[0-5]	0
D2	[5-8]	0.03
D3	[8-8.5]	4
D4	[8.5-9]	41
D5	[9-9.5]	390

4.3 PFM results

First, the model results are compared to experimental results. Once good agreement is achieved the numerical model can be used to probe quantities and provide insight into phenomena that are difficult or impossible to measure experimentally. Specifically, the model is used to investigate the air impurity effect on the density of short-lived species, the reaction rates of long-lived species, and the discharge dynamics.

4.3.1 Comparison with experimental results

In Figure 10 the PFM simulation results show good agreement with experimental measurements in terms of electrical characteristics (current, voltage, and phase). The comparison is done at the input power of 30 W corresponding to an RMS voltage of 331 V and for the entire discharge gap that includes all the different impurity domains (D1-D6).

Figure 10: Voltage/current waveform comparison between simulation and experiment. The waveforms of the simulation are the superposition of waveforms of 6 simulations at different impurity levels.

Furthermore, as it will be seen in Appendix C, there is a good agreement between simulation results and emission spectroscopy measurements. That coupled with the electrical measurement matching gives us confidence that the numerical model is capable of reproducing the discharge physics of this device. Therefore, it can be used to probe quantities such as density of different reactive species inside the discharge region that are too difficult to measure.

A variety of short-lived and long-lived reactive species that are important for different applications, such as plasma medicine are studied. Considering that the simulation accounts for 100 μ s of discharge, the evolution of short-lived species can reach a steady state, thus allowing the analysis of

the density of those species. The density of the long-lived species, however, need more time to reach a quasi-steady state and therefore only their production and destruction kinetics are presented.

4.3.2 Air impurity influence on the density of short-lived species

Species such as O, N, N₂(C), and H have a short lifetime and thus their average densities in a plasma with different air impurities can be studied. The effect of air impurities on the averaged density of the negative species is presented in Figure 11. The six points correspond to the six domains presented in Table 2. D1 which corresponds to 0 ppm is represented with 10⁻³ due to the logarithmic scale. The term average means both time-averaged over one RF cycle and space averaged along the gap (2 mm). As it was done in literature [16][27] the air impurity level instead of space coordinate is used in the following figures to demonstrate the influence of air impurities on the plasma chemistry.

As can be seen from Figure 11, electrons are the most abundant negative species in the plasma. Close to the nozzle edge, the electron density exhibits a slight decrease. This is mainly due to the high increase of air impurities in this region that enhances the electron attachment processes (explained in [31]). The electron attachment mainly takes place with O₂ and H₂O molecules close to the nozzle exit and thereby an increase of these species and their byproducts (O⁻, O₂⁻, O₃⁻, OH⁻ and H₂O₂⁻) are observed. The negative species (H⁻, H₃O₂⁻ and H₅O₃⁻) that are mainly produced through water species also increase close to the exit.

Figure 12 illustrates the effect of air impurities on the positive ions. At low levels of air impurities (i.e. D1 and D2), the most abundant ion is the He₂⁺. This is consistent with previous studies [32,33]. As the level of air increases in the mixture, He₂⁺ is quickly converted to N₂⁺ (see the schematic diagram of Figure 6 in [31]). For that reason, in the range of air between 0.5 – 10 ppm, the N₂⁺ becomes the most abundant ion. At higher levels of air, the nitrogen ions are quickly converted to oxygen ions (as shown and explained in [27,31]). For that reason, the O₂⁺ becomes the dominant ion close to the nozzle exit (for the level of air > 10 ppm). The water ions also show an increase at the exit. The most dominant species are H₂O₃⁺, H₇O₃⁺, H₉O₄⁺, H₄O₂⁺, H₅O₂⁺, H₃O⁺, and H₁₁O₅⁺, which are the first water species generated as observed in literature [27].

Figure 11: Density of short-lived negative species variation with air impurities.

Figure 12: Density of short-lived positive species variation with air impurities.

As for the short-lived radicals such as O, N, H, and $N_2(C)$ species, oxygen radicals are the most abundant radicals in the discharge zone, which is also found in the literature [18]. As shown in Figure 13, the densities of O, N, $N_2(C)$ increase with air and water impurities at the exit of the plasma.

Figure 13: Density variation of short-lived species with air impurities.

4.3.3 Air impurity influences on the kinetics of long-lived species

Long-lived species such as H_2O_2 molecules and $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ radicals are important for biomedical applications or surface treatment as they can be transported to long distances from the active plasma region and play a major role in plasma/surface interaction. For long-lived species, reaction rates instead of density results are presented because of large relaxation times and their densities did not reach steady state by the end of the 100 μs simulation. The air impurity effects on the production and destruction of H_2O_2 are illustrated in Figure 14. As can be seen from Figure 14, the main contribution to H_2O_2 production comes from the dimerization of OH radicals. The rate of this reaction increases, due to the increase of OH density. On the other hand, the total destruction rates of H_2O_2 species decrease with air impurities. Among reactions contributing to the H_2O_2 destruction, Penning ionization between He^m and H_2O_2 dominate the destruction rates in most of the discharge channel. However, close to the outlet of the device, He^m is mainly lost due to reactions associated with nitrogen and oxygen species, thus limiting the contribution of He^m in reactions with H_2O_2 . In addition, near the outlet of the device, the dissociation of H_2O_2 by electron impact plays a role but with a decreasing trend. This is due to the decrease of electrons density along the discharge towards the outlet. The H_2O_2 destruction reaction rates with OH and O^1D show upward trends. This is reasonable as at the exit of the discharge, OH and O^1D increase due to the increase of O_2 .

Figure 14: Average reaction rates of H_2O_2 production (left) and destruction (right).

Among other species, singlet oxygen is considered to be very important for biomedical applications. The $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ production rate is mainly defined by the direct excitation of O_2 through the electron impact. As air impurity increases, more O_2 from air is present in the discharge, leading to a higher $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ production rate (see Figure 15 (left)). Furthermore, close to the outlet, an important reaction for the production of $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ starts to be also through the $\text{N}_2(\text{A})$. The destruction rate also increases with air impurities, as shown in Figure 15 (right). The dominant reaction to destruct $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ is the quenching between $\text{O}(^1\text{S})$ and $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$, to form O_2 and O . Overall, the closer to the outlet, the higher the reaction rates are for both production and destruction.

Figure 15: Average reaction rates of $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ production (left) and destruction (right).

4.3.4 Time resolved discharge dynamics

As discussed in section 4.3.2, the production of RONS is closely related to the electron impact processes, which are also dependent on discharge dynamics. Electric fields and ionization rates are two

essential parameters of the discharge dynamics. As presented in Figure 16, time resolved dynamics of electric fields in the gap are obtained under two discharge conditions with air impurity of 0 ppm (at the inlet) and 3683 ppm (at the outlet). It is noticed that the electric field is strong in the sheath and drastically decreases to several Tds in the plasma bulk. The electric field follows the periodical variation with RF voltage. The time resolved electric field evolution pattern is similar for both conditions. However, as air impurity increases, the maximum electric field in the gap at 0 ppm condition (see Figure 16(a)) is 12.2 Td higher than that at 3683 ppm condition (see Figure 16(b)). Similar phenomenon is also observed in our work [31]. Because the electronegative gases (O_2 , H_2O) are introduced from air impurities in this work, effective electron attachment processes will result in a decrease of electron density and a weakened space charge effect that leads to the reduction of the local electric field.

Figure 16: Air impurity influences on the reduced electric fields: (a) 0 ppm; (b) 3683 ppm. Unit of electric field is Td.

Time resolved ionization rates in the gap were studied for the discharge for both 0 ppm and 3683 ppm (see Figure 17). Although ionization rates follow the RF cycles, the evolution patterns for both conditions are different, indicating that a high amount of humid air intrusion can result in different discharge kinetics at the outlet. Strong ionization occurs near the sheath for both conditions. However, the maximum ionization rate for 0 ppm (see Figure 17(a)) is 1.75 times that for 3683 ppm (see Figure 17(b)). Instead of a concentrated ionization region near the sheath, discharges with a higher amount of air impurities are prone to have more diffuse ionization regions into the plasma bulk. Considering the strong stabilization effect of the sheath on the RF discharge [29], one can expect that air intrusion is a major instability factor. Therefore, care should be given to the design and operation of RF plasma sources exposed in the open air in order to avoid high intrusion of the air in the active region of the discharge and transition to γ -mode. It should be mentioned that this effect is not seen in Figure 7 where the entire emission (integrated over the gap region) is measured.

Figure 17: Air impurity influences on ionization rates: (a) 0 ppm; (b) 3683 ppm. Unit: mol/(m³s)

5. Conclusions

An atmospheric pressure RF helium planar plasma source is investigated experimentally and numerically in order to reveal the impact of air impurities on plasma properties and the generation of reactive species. The plasma can be sustained as a diffuse RF α -mode discharge at relatively low gas temperatures. A novel methodology by converting the 2D plasma simulation into six 1D plasma simulations enables the investigation of non-uniformly distributed air impurity influences on the RF plasma. The numerical results have good agreement with electrical discharge and emission spectroscopy measurements. Numerical modelling was used to get insights into the air impurity effects on the density of short-lived species and reaction rates of long-lived species, as well as the discharge dynamics. The modelling of the plasma kinetics as a function of air impurities along the discharge gap revealed that He_2^+ are the major positive ions formed in the region close to the inlet whereas O_2^+ ions start to play the leading role near the outlet. The density of water cluster ions $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n\text{H}^+$ with $n < 2$ was found to be significantly affected from air impurities with H_2O^+ being dominant in the region with low air intrusion and H_2O_3^+ being dominant in the outlet of the source. $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ production is mainly supported through the direct electron excitation of molecular O_2 while its destruction is mainly ascribed to the quenching between $\text{O}(^1\text{S})$ and $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$. Both production and destruction rates of $\text{O}_2(\text{a})$ were found to increase towards the outlet, where air impurities increase. H_2O_2 , an important species in biomedical applications, mainly originates from the combination of OH radicals. The destruction kinetics of H_2O_2 is mainly ascribed to the Penning ionization between He_m and H_2O_2 in the discharge gap and close to the outlet; however, the dissociation of H_2O_2 by electron collisions becomes dominant at the outlet. Furthermore, it was found that increased air impurity level decreases the electric fields and ionization rates in the discharge gap and can lead to instability of the discharge.

The method proposed in this work, combining flow dynamics simulation and plasma fluid model, deepens the understandings of RF helium plasma jets and clarifies the effect of the ambient humid air

intrusion on the reactive species kinetics and discharge stability. The proposed methodology can be extended to study RF plasma sources and plasma chemistry with admixing air and to optimize the output of reactive species at the outlet.

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Appendix A

Table A1: Determination of air impurities at each domain.

Species	Air back diffusion ^a	Helium Bottle (ppm) ^b	Total (ppm)
N ₂	78% of air	1	0.78*air+1
O ₂	21% of air	0.01	0.21*air+0.01
H ₂ O	1% of air ^c	0.02	0.01*air+0.02

^a)Air impurities due to back flow calculated from the GDM. Their values at the different domains are presented in Table 2.

^b)The air impurities from the helium bottle are determined based on the supplier specifications as following: 1 ppm N₂, 0.01 ppm O₂, and 0.02 ppm H₂O.

^c)The relative humidity is 60%.

Figure A1: 16 trigger timings in an RF cycle used for ICCD imaging of the emission patterns.

Figure A2: Simulation domain for 1D plasma fluid model.

Appendix B: Gas temperature determination

Determining the gas temperature is important for improving the accuracy of the numerical model and to ensure that this plasma is suitable for bio-applications or heat-sensitive material processing, where low temperature is required. Gas temperatures can be typically estimated from fitting the emission of molecular bands. The OH($A^2\Sigma^+ \rightarrow X^2\Pi$, 0-0) band is used to evaluate the rotational temperature which also indicates gas temperature [28,34,35]. The OH band from 306-312 nm is simulated and fitted with experimental spectra, shown in Figure B1(a). The best fitting of the experimental spectra with the simulated ones using the massiveOES software [36,37] ranges from 340 K to 375 ± 25 K with the power varying from 10 W to 30 W. The corresponding Boltzmann plot for the rotational quantum number ($N < 12$) confirms the rotational temperature, given in Figure B1(b). The estimated gas temperature is used in the numerical simulations (for both the GDM and PFM). The temperature confirms that this α -mode type of plasma operated is suitable for bio applications and heat sensitive material processing.

Figure B1: Gas temperature estimation: (a) OH emission bands from experiment and simulation with massiveOES; (b) corresponding Boltzmann plot from OH bands.

Appendix C: Line emission evolution

Photon counting techniques were adopted to record line emission evolution of the discharge, which is further used to compare with simulation results.

Figure C1: Optical emission spectroscopy for the atmospheric pressure RF helium plasma: emission lines intensity evolution recorded through photon counting technique for O I 777nm, He I at 706 nm, $N_2^+(B)$ at 391 nm, $N_2(C)$ at 337 nm, OH at 309 nm.

Figure C2: Depopulation rates of transition for (a) He I at 706nm; (b) $N_2(C)$ at 337 nm; (c) $N_2^+(B)$ 391 at nm; (d) O I at 777 nm; (e) OH(A) at 309 nm.

Specifically, the following transitions were used to compare emission patterns between experiments and simulation for the 0 ppm condition: He I ($^3S \rightarrow ^3P^o$) at 706nm, $N_2(C)$ ($C^3P_u(v'=0) \rightarrow B^3P_g(v'=0)$) at 337 nm, $N_2^+(B)$ ($B^2\Sigma_u(v'=0) \rightarrow X^2\Sigma_g(v'=0)$) at 391 nm, O I ($^5P \rightarrow ^5S^o$) at 777 nm and OH(A) ($A^2\Sigma^+(v'=0) \rightarrow X^2\Pi(v'=0)$) at 309 nm. It is obvious that the depopulation rates of the transition of He I at 706 nm, $N_2(C)$ at 337 nm, $N_2^+(B)$ at 391 nm, and O I at 777 nm as seen in Figure C2(a-d) are evolving periodically whereas the OH(A) transition rate is non-periodic as seen in Figure C2(e). These numerical results are in good agreement with results from photon counting techniques seen in Figure C1.

References

- [1] Winter J, Brandenburg R and Weltmann K-D 2015 Atmospheric pressure plasma jets: an overview of devices and new directions *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **24** 064001
- [2] Cvelbar U, Walsh J L, Černák M, de Vries H W, Reuter S, Belmonte T, Corbella C, Miron C, Hojnik N, Jurov A, Puliyalil H, Gorjanc M, Portal S, Laurita R, Colombo V, Schäfer J, Nikiforov A, Modic M, Kylian O, Polak M, Labay C, Canal J M, Canal C, Gherardi M, Bazaka K, Sonar P, Ostrikov K K, Cameron D, Thomas S and Weltmann K 2019 White paper on the future of plasma science and technology in plastics and textiles *Plasma Process. Polym.* **16** 1700228
- [3] Brandenburg R, Bogaerts A, Bongers W, Fridman A, Fridman G, Locke B R, Miller V, Reuter S, Schiorlin M, Verreycken T and Ostrikov K (Ken) 2019 White paper on the future of plasma science in environment, for gas conversion and agriculture *Plasma Process. Polym.* **16** 1700238
- [4] Fanelli F and Fracassi F 2017 Atmospheric pressure non-equilibrium plasma jet technology: general features, specificities and applications in surface processing of materials *Surf. Coatings Technol.* **322** 174–201
- [5] Zhu W-C, Li Q, Zhu X-M and Pu Y-K 2009 Characteristics of atmospheric pressure plasma jets emerging into ambient air and helium *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* **42** 202002
- [6] Schröder M, Ochoa A and Breitkopf C 2015 Numerical simulation of an atmospheric pressure RF-driven plasma needle and heat transfer to adjacent human skin using COMSOL *Biointerphases* **10** 029508
- [7] Schröter S, Gibson A R, Kushner M J, Gans T and O'Connell D 2018 Numerical study of the influence of surface reaction probabilities on reactive species in an rf atmospheric pressure plasma containing humidity *Plasma Phys. Control. Fusion* **60** 014035
- [8] Alves L L and Bogaerts A 2017 Special issue on numerical modelling of low-temperature plasmas for various applications - Part I: review and tutorial papers on numerical modelling approaches *Plasma Process. Polym.* **14** 1690011

- [9] Engeln R, Klarenaar B and Guaitella O 2020 Foundations of optical diagnostics in low-temperature plasmas *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **29** 063001
- [10] Alves L L, Bogaerts A, Guerra V and Turner M M 2018 Foundations of modelling of nonequilibrium low-temperature plasmas *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27** 023002
- [11] Van Laer K and Bogaerts A 2016 Fluid modelling of a packed bed dielectric barrier discharge plasma reactor *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **25** 015002
- [12] Lu X, Naidis G V, Laroussi M, Reuter S, Graves D B and Ostrikov K 2016 Reactive species in non-equilibrium atmospheric-pressure plasmas: Generation, transport, and biological effects *Phys. Rep.* **630** 1–84
- [13] Bischoff L, Hübner G, Korolov I, Donkó Z, Hartmann P, Gans T, Held J, Schulz-von der Gathen V, Liu Y, Mussenbrock T and Schulze J 2018 Experimental and computational investigations of electron dynamics in micro atmospheric pressure radio-frequency plasma jets operated in He/N₂ mixtures *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27** 125009
- [14] Niermann B, Hemke T, Babaeva N Y, Böke M, Kushner M J, Mussenbrock T and Winter J 2011 Spatial dynamics of helium metastables in sheath or bulk dominated rf micro-plasma jets *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **44** 485204
- [15] Hemke T, Wollny A, Gebhardt M, Brinkmann R P and Mussenbrock T 2011 Spatially resolved simulation of a radio-frequency driven micro-atmospheric pressure plasma jet and its effluent *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **44** 285206
- [16] Schröter S, Wijakhum A, Gibson A R, West A, Davies H L, Minesi N, Dedrick J, Wagenaars E, de Oliveira N, Nahon L, Kushner M J, Booth J-P, Niemi K, Gans T and O’Connell D 2018 Chemical kinetics in an atmospheric pressure helium plasma containing humidity *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **20** 24263–86
- [17] Sun B, Liu D, Iza F, Wang S, Yang A, Liu Z, Rong M and Wang X 2019 Global model of an atmospheric-pressure capacitive discharge in helium with air impurities from 100 to 10 000 ppm *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **28** 035006
- [18] Liu Y, Liu D, Zhang J, Sun B, Yang A and Kong M G 2020 1D fluid model of RF-excited cold atmospheric plasmas in helium with air gas impurities *Phys. Plasmas* **27** 043512
- [19] COMSOL AB COMSOL Multiphysics® v. 4.4 <https://www.comsol.com/plasma-module>
- [20] Dewan M N A, McNally P J and Herbert P A F 2002 Plasma modeling for a nonsymmetric capacitive discharge driven by a nonsinusoidal radio frequency current *J. Appl. Phys.* **91** 5604–13
- [21] Vyalykh D V., Dubinov A E, Zhdanov V S, L’vov I L, Sadovoi S A and Selemir V D 2013 Observation of nonlinear generation of higher RF harmonics in hollow-cathode discharge *Tech. Phys. Lett.* **39** 217–9

- [22] Pascal C and Nicholas B 2011 *Physics of radio-frequency plasmas* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press)
- [23] Lieberman M A and Lichtenberg A J 2005 *Principles of plasma discharges and materials processing* (Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.)
- [24] Laimer J and Störi H 2006 Glow discharges observed in capacitive radio-frequency atmospheric-pressure plasma jets *Plasma Process. Polym.* **3** 573–86
- [25] Ashraf H, Shah S Z A, Qazi H I A, Khan M A, Hussain S, BADAR M A, Niaz S and Shafiq M 2019 Electrical features of radio-frequency atmospheric pressure helium discharge with and without dielectric electrodes *Plasma Sci. Technol.* **21** 025403
- [26] Lazarou C, Anastassiou C, Topala I, Chiper A S, Mihaila I, Pohoata V and Georghiou G E 2018 Numerical simulation of capillary helium and helium–oxygen atmospheric pressure plasma jets: propagation dynamics and interaction with dielectric *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27** 105007
- [27] Lazarou C, Chiper A S, Anastassiou C, Topala I, Mihaila I, Pohoata V and Georghiou G E 2019 Numerical simulation of the effect of water admixtures on the evolution of a helium/dry air discharge *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **52** 195203
- [28] Deng X, Nikiforov A Y, Ionita E-R, Dinescu G and Leys C 2015 Absolute and relative emission spectroscopy study of 3 cm wide planar radio frequency atmospheric pressure bio-plasma source *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **107** 053702
- [29] Wang L, Dinescu G, Deng X, Ionita E-R, Leys C and Nikiforov A Y 2017 Mechanisms of sustaining a radio-frequency atmospheric pressure planar discharge *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **26** 075012
- [30] Mahony C M O, Al Wazzan R and Graham W G 1997 Sheath dynamics observed in a 13.56 MHz-driven plasma *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **71** 608–10
- [31] Lazarou C, Belmonte T, Chiper A S and Georghiou G E 2016 Numerical modelling of the effect of dry air traces in a helium parallel plate dielectric barrier discharge *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **25** 055023
- [32] Lazarou C, Koukounis D, Chiper A S, Costin C, Topala I and Georghiou G E 2015 Numerical modeling of the effect of the level of nitrogen impurities in a helium parallel plate dielectric barrier discharge *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **24** 035012
- [33] Martens T, Bogaerts A, Brok W J M and Dijk J V. 2008 The dominant role of impurities in the composition of high pressure noble gas plasmas *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **92** 041504
- [34] Xiong Q, Nikiforov A, Britun N, Snyders R, Leys C and Lu X 2011 A simple profile-fitting method to determine the metastable and resonant densities in a cold atmospheric pressure argon plasma jet *J. Appl. Phys.* **110** 073302

- [35] Bruggeman P J, Sadeghi N, Schram D C and Linss V 2014 Gas temperature determination from rotational lines in non-equilibrium plasmas: a review *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **23** 023001
- [36] Voráč J and Synek P 2016 massiveOES software package https://bitbucket.org/OES_muni/massiveoes
- [37] Voráč J, Synek P, Procházka V and Hoder T 2017 State-by-state emission spectra fitting for non-equilibrium plasmas: OH spectra of surface barrier discharge at argon/water interface *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.* **50** 294002